

DigInTraCE

Communication and Dissemination plan and activities D7.8

DigInTraCE

A Digital value chain Integration Traceability framework for process industries for Circularity and low Emissions by waste reduction and use of secondary raw materials

Funded by
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DigInTraCE

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
WPx	Work Package x
Dx.y.	Deliverable x.y.
Tx.y.	Task x.y.
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
No.	Number
PMs	Person - months
Q&A	Questions & Answers
DPP	Digital Product Passport

Executive Summary

Funded under Horizon Europe, DigInTraCE aims to provide solutions to achieve low emissions and promote circularity through waste reduction and secondary raw materials use. The project will leverage innovative tracking, sensing and sorting techniques to develop a transparent and interoperable decentralised traceability platform, focusing on the pulp and paper and chemicals sectors. The project will also develop dynamically updated DPP schemes supporting certification, quality validation, AI-based decision-making mechanisms for process and life cycle optimisation, and up-cycling, reuse and upgrade technologies for improved secondary raw materials use. DigInTraCE will specifically focus on composite wood and furniture, wood and pulp and paper, plastic parts from ICT equipment and the automotive market, as well as polymers and textiles.

WP7 'Guidance, Training, Cooperation, Exploitation and communication' aims to contribute to the standardization and certification of secondary materials and digital technologies. It also focuses on co-designing training activities and lifelong learning programmes on digital skills, identifying and studying best practices, developing replication guidelines and methodologies with technical and practical information to replicate a successful case, developing exploitation activities and business models, performing IPR Management and implementing DigInTraCE dissemination and communication activities.

This deliverable, 'D7.8 Communication and Dissemination Plan v1', is part of Task 7.4 'Dissemination and communication activities, policy recommendations. The document provides a step-by-step outline of the communication and dissemination plan to be followed in DigInTraCE. It includes the definition of the main objectives for communication and dissemination, identifying key target audiences, determining the messages to be conveyed, selecting the means and channels of communication, outlining the dissemination processes, and introducing the initial communication and dissemination tools created to maximize awareness and effectively communicate the project's messages to stakeholders.

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This document will serve as a guideline for all project partners, encouraging their participation in disseminating the project and its messages to the target audiences according to their role and individual plans within the project.

1. Introduction

Before starting to elaborate on the communication and dissemination plan of DigInTraCE, it is critical to understand the project's concept. To achieve this, the first chapter of this deliverable will provide an overview of the project, outlining its major outputs. Following that, the document's scope will be analysed, presenting the intended readership, the structure of the document and its relation with other deliverables and tasks.

1.1. DigInTraCE Overview

Process industries are actively working towards finding solutions to achieve low emissions and promote circularity by reducing waste and utilizing secondary raw materials. The EU-funded DigInTraCE project aims to employ innovative tracking, sensing and sorting techniques to develop a transparent and interoperable decentralised traceability platform focusing on the pulp and paper and chemicals sectors. The project will also develop dynamically updated DPP schemes supporting certification, quality validation, AI-based decision-making mechanisms for process and life cycle optimisation, and up-cycling, reuse and upgrade technologies for improved secondary raw materials use. DigInTraCE will concentrate on composite wood and furniture, wood and pulp and paper, plastic parts from ICT equipment and the automotive market, as well as polymers and textiles.

1.2. Document scope

D7.8 Dissemination and Communication Plan presents an overview of the DigInTraCE communication and dissemination objectives and the framework for coordinating all planned dissemination and communication activities throughout the project's lifetime. Furthermore, it identifies the target groups, channels and tools to be utilized in order to effectively reach them and achieve a high level of impact for the project and its results, as well as to create awareness.

As communication and dissemination requires teamwork, it is crucial for all partners to be familiar with the opportunities and procedures. Therefore, this document serves as a guideline providing all the necessary information regarding Dissemination and Communication. All processes and procedures are in accordance with the Consortium Agreement and the Horizon Europe Communication and Dissemination guidelines.

1.3. Intended Readership

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This deliverable is publicly disseminated and intended for a wide readership, including the DigInTraCE consortium members, European Commission representatives, interested parties, and the general public.

It will serve as a valuable reference for consortium members in planning the project's dissemination and communication activities, thereby enhancing awareness about DigInTraCE.

1.4. Document structure

The deliverable D7.8 Communication and Dissemination plan and activities v1 is comprised of 6 chapters and 4 annexes. The first chapter serves as an introduction to DigInTraCE project, outlining the scope of the current deliverable, the target audience, its relation to other WP7 deliverables and tasks, and defining key concepts. The second chapter presents the Communication and Dissemination Strategy, including the approach, objectives, key audiences and key messages per audience. The fourth chapter highlights the most suitable communication and dissemination channels and tools to effectively reach all target audiences. Chapter five provides an overview of the implementation of the Communication and Dissemination plan throughout the project's duration. The conclusion forms the last chapter.

1.5. Relationship with other Deliverables and Tasks

The following tables present the relationship of D7.8 Communication and Dissemination plan and activities with the other deliverables of Task 7.4 and with other WP7 deliverables in general.

Table 1, Relationship between D7.8 and other Task 7.4 deliverables

Deliverable	Relationship	Example
D7.9 – Communication and Dissemination plan and activities v2	A Communication and Dissemination Plan will be developed to present the project's concept and outcomes to the general public and address a wide audience. Furthermore, the appropriate communication and dissemination channels will be determined.	D7.8 consists the initial communication and dissemination strategy of the project. D7.9 will use this as a prototype and customise it based on the project developments.
D7.10 – Communication and Dissemination plan and activities FINAL	The final version of the communication and dissemination plan and activities will be developed by the end of the project so as to	D7.8 consists the initial communication and dissemination strategy of the project, so it will be used as the initial version to customise the total

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	include all the latest developments and planning.	communication and dissemination strategy of the project.
D7.11 – Policy briefs	DigInTraCE will develop 2 policy briefs for the focal sectors us: pulp and paper, chemicals and plastics. These policy briefs consist a dissemination activity since it is an effort to disseminate the project results.	D7.8 sets the basis for the development of each dissemination activity, including the policy briefs.

Table 2, Relationship of D7.8 with other WP7 deliverables

Deliverable	Relationship	Example
D7.3 Co-design training activities and lifelong learning programmes on digital skills and replication v1	Training activities and lifelong learning are integral parts of Task 7.2. However, these activities are closely interrelated with dissemination as they serve as dissemination activities of the project. Therefore, close collaboration among the Task leaders is crucial to effectively organise these activities, taking into consideration the D7.8 Communication and Dissemination Plan.	D7.8 sets the basis for the organisation of all dissemination and communication activities related to DigInTraCE.
D7.4 Co-design training activities and lifelong learning programmes on digital skills and replication FINAL		

2. Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Communication and Dissemination are both key elements of any Horizon Europe project. The table below presents their differences based on the European IP Helpdesk.

Table 3, Communication and Dissemination definitions and differences

	Communication	Dissemination
Definition	Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. <i>(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)</i>	The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including scientific publications in any medium. <i>(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)</i>
Objectives	Reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities, e.g., by addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges.	Transfer knowledge & results to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximizing EU-funded research.
Focus	Inform about and promote the project and its results/success.	Describe and ensure results available for others to use. Focus given on results only
Target Audiences	Multiple audiences beyond the 'project's	Audiences that may take an interest in the

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	own community incl. Media and the broad public.	potential use of the results (e.g., the scientific community, industrial partners, policymakers).
Formal Obligations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rules for Participants • RIA & IA Proposal Template 2.2 b) • Grant Agreement Art. 38.1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rules for Participants • RIA & IA Proposal Template 2.2 a) • Grant Agreement Art. 29

The Communication and Dissemination Strategy is a fundamental tool in the hands of the project partners to raise awareness of the project's concept and key activities and maximize the societal impact and benefits among the target groups. The purpose of the DigInTraCE Communication and Dissemination Strategy is to ensure that all planned communication activities align with the core objectives of the project and consistently deliver key messages. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to define a strategy from the early stages of the project to allocate resources efficiently to specific activities.

The strategy includes defining objectives and identifying key audiences. Tailored key messages are being drafted for different key audiences to maximize impact. Additionally, various communication channels to reach these key audiences are being identified, along with KPIs to monitor the effects of the performed activities.

2.1. Communication Approach

The communication approach of DigInTraCE follows a five-step approach, encompassing key communication elements such as audience, messages, tools, channels and a time plan. Additionally, an evaluation process is included to monitor and measure the project's progress, ensuring the effectiveness of the communication strategy and allowing for necessary adjustments if needed.

The DigInTraCE communication strategy is built upon the Laswell model by answering five simple questions:

- Which are the key audiences;
- Which are their needs;
- What do we need to communicate to them – our messages;
- What are the most effective channels to deliver these messages;
- What are the results of our actions.

By implementing this approach, the project aims to maximize its impact on all targeted audiences.

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Figure 1, The Laswell model

In terms of timeline, DiGInTraCE will follow a three-phase approach throughout the project's duration. The initial phase will primarily focus on reaching the targeted audiences and providing general information about the project's concept, objectives and expected outcomes. The second phase will build upon the first phase by monitoring and evaluating the initial activities. Furthermore, during this phase and with availability of initial results, tailored promotion efforts will be initiated to engage each stakeholder group more effectively. Finally, in the third phase, a significant effort will be dedicated to effectively disseminate the project results to all target audiences, ensuring the long-term impact of the project's final outcomes and results.

Chapter 5.2 of this deliverable will establish a communication and dissemination roadmap and action plan.

2.2. Communication Objectives

When designing the DigInTraCE communication strategy, the first and most fundamental step is to define its objectives and the associated activities planned to achieve these objectives.

According to the GA, the communication objectives for DigInTraCE can be summarised as follows:

Table 4, Communication Objectives

Objectives
✓ Contribute to standardization and certification of secondary materials and digital technologies
✓ Co-design training activities and lifelong learning programmes on digital skills
✓ Identify and study the best practices
✓ Develop replication guidelines and methodology with technical and practical information to replicate a successful case

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✓ **Develop exploitation activities and business models**

✓ **Perform IPR Management**

✓ **Develop dissemination and communication activities.**

2.3. Key audiences

The detailed definition of the target groups is crucial as it helps in directing resources towards the most relevant and interested actors, thereby maximising the potential impact of the project.

Table 5, DigInTraCE Key audiences

S/A	Key audiences
1	Policy makers & Public authorities
2	EU Public Bodies
3	Processes4Planet (P4Planet) Partnership stakeholders
4	Environmental Partnerships, Associations, Initiatives
5	Industrial stakeholders (producers, process industries, manufacturers, intermediates, recyclers, etc.)
6	Plastic Convertors Association
7	Scientific & Research Community
8	Other Eu funded projects
9	General Public
10	Press

2.4. Key messages

There are several key messages that partners can utilise throughout the course of the project to effectively present DigInTraCE. This approach is valuable in providing a consistent branding of the project. However, it is important to consider that the key messages should serve as a foundation, and be adapted based on the specific audience being addressed, as well as the project's needs and status.

2.4.1. General message

DigInTraCE aims at the development of i)transparent and interoperable Decentralized Traceability platform using novel tracking, sensing and sorting techniques ii)Dynamically updated DPP schemes supporting certification and quality validation iii)AI based and decision making mechanisms for process and lifecycle optimisation iv)up-cycling, reuse and upgrade technologies for improved secondary raw materials use v)contribute to standardization, open and easy accessible data vi)business models creating new economic opportunities and learning resources for employees, promoting new digital skills and meeting regional social needs. The solutions are developed at TRL6 by the end of the project and demonstrated in the sectors of a) Pulp & Paper focused in 2 cases: composite wood and furniture; and wood and Pulp & Paper and b) Chemicals focused in 2

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cases: plastic parts for ICT equipment and automotive market; and polymers & textiles.

2.4.2. Keywords

In this section are identified the keywords describing the main concept of the project: Computer sciences, information science, bioinformatics, quality validation, lifecycle optimization, circular economy, sustainability.

2.4.3. Tailored key messages

A set of key messages has been developed for each target audience (Table 5), taking into account their needs and specific characteristics. The tailored key messages are presented in the graphic below.

Figure 2, Key messages per audience

3. Project identity

The DigInTraCE project will establish a strong project identity by implementing effective branding strategies and delivering clear messages to diverse target audiences. To achieve this, a project logo, project templates and a dedicated brand book have been created to ensure consistent brand identity. These branding elements will be utilized across various Communication and Dissemination channels such as the project website, leaflets, posters, templates, and presentations to promote the project.

3.1. Brand identity

The logo serves as the core element of the project. A dedicated logo (Figure 2) has been agreed upon by the project partners from the beginning of the project. A specific selection process was followed to conclude on the selected one. According to the process, each organisation voted among three logos (Annex 3) to finally select the current one. The logo acts as a trademark, promoting instant public recognition and eliciting reactions from viewers right from the initial communication and dissemination activities.

Figure 3, DigInTraCE logo

The logo was deliberately designed to be simple, easily recognizable and comprehensible, allowing people to instantly grasp the main idea of the project. It represents the project's focus on environmental sustainability, circularity, and reducing emissions through waste reduction and the use of secondary raw materials. The circular shape of the logo symbolizes the concept of circularity and the idea of a complete value chain. The color palette was specifically chosen to include earthy tones, aligning with environmental projects. The brand typography utilises the Montserrat font.

Figure 4, Other logo formats

3.2. Color palette

Alongside the selection of the DigInTraCE logo, a carefully chosen range of colors was specified from the very beginning of the project. The colors were selected in alignment with the main concept of the project. Maintaining a cohesive use of colors in both print and digital materials ensures a strong and consistent visual presence for the project.

Figure 5, DigInTraCE logo color guide

3.3. Document Templates

A set of DigInTraCE MS office templates has been created based on the project's brand to be utilised in both internal and external events. Specifically, a PowerPoint presentation template has been developed for use in both project internal meetings and external presentations. Moreover, a Word Deliverable template has been prepared for submitting DigInTraCE deliverables, and a Meeting Minutes

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template has been created for documenting minutes during Consortium meetings. All templates are accessible to all partners on the Teams Work Space and are also provided in Annex 1 of this document.

4. Communication and Dissemination Channels, Tools and Activities

This section provides an overview of the DigInTraCE communication tools, as well as the KPIs agreed in the GA for each tool separately.

4.1. Online channels

In recent times, online communication has emerged as the most efficient method for promoting and disseminating events, projects, organizations etc. Therefore, online communication tools and channels (such as the project's website, social media, newsletter, etc.) have been identified as the main channels for communication and dissemination in DigInTraCE. These channels not only provide a cost-effective means to reach a wide audience at the European and international levels, but also enable a more efficient and dynamic form of communication., They allow for tailored messages to different target groups and facilitate interaction between the project and its stakeholders.

This sub-section presents some of the main online tools and channels that will be utilized throughout the project's duration.

4.1.1. Website

The project's website serves as the most crucial communication channel and acts as the backbone for all communication and dissemination activities. It functions as the primary gateway for all interested parties and facilitates engagement with the identified key audiences.

Figure 6, The DigInTraCE website

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The website has been designed to be minimal, user-friendly and easily navigable. Its structure allows for future scalability and quick expansion. It has been accessible at <https://www.digintrace.eu/> since M03 and will remain active for three years beyond the project's end, providing interested parties with the opportunity to stay updated on the project's developments and outcomes. Google Analytics will be implemented to measure website traffic and provide valuable statistics.

The website presents the project's concept, objectives, methodology, partners, demonstrators, events and news. It will host all public deliverables, scientific publications, DigInTraCE dissemination materials, and downloadable newsletters for visitors to access. The website will be frequently updated to reflect the project's developments.

To monitor the effectiveness of the website, the following KPIs related to visitor engagement have been identified:

Table 6, Unique website visitors

Unique Visitors	
from M12	from M36
>1,500	>5,500

4.1.2. Social media accounts

This project will extensively utilise social media platforms, namely LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube to raise awareness about DigInTraCE, communicate the project's progress and results, and share news and activities. Additionally, all partners will be encouraged to promote the project through their respective organizations' social media channels. Furthermore, other social media platforms such as Facebook, TikTok etc. will be used for wider community engagement.

Table 7, Social media related KPIs

Social media	
Size of online community (M36)	No. of impressions (monthly average)
>5,000	>500

4.1.2.1. LinkedIn

LinkedIn is considered the most popular professional network on the internet. Registered members have the opportunity to connect with professionals who share similar interests and engage in group discussions.

DigInTraCE maintains a LinkedIn page available [here](#), with the goal of establishing a robust network among key audiences of the project and interacting with individuals involved in the circular economy sector. Figure 7 provides an overview of the DigInTrace LinkedIn profile.

Figure 7, LinkedIn page

4.1.2.2. Twitter

Twitter is a social networking platform primarily used as a news source and real-time conversation hub for trending topics. @digintrace actively engages with relevant accounts and promotes the project's vision and developments.

Figure 8, DigInTraCE twitter account

4.1.2.3. YouTube

A YouTube account for DigInTrace will be created during the project and will serve as the repository for all project videos.

4.2. Communication kit

4.2.1. Brochure, Roll-up banner

The project will develop promotional material to promote its concept and objectives during events. The material will be produced throughout the project's duration, based on the project's requirements, starting from M03.

The first version of the roll-up banner has already been created and is available on the website and online repository. The banner has been designed to align with the project's brand identity, with a focus on minimalism and attractive design. It includes key information about the project, such as its facts and full title, EU funding, social media presence, as well as information about the consortium partners.

Figure 9, DigInTraCE roll-up banner

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The roll-up banner will be used as a visually appealing display at project-related or external events. Moreover, a brochure will be designed to provide comprehensive information about the project to interested parties. The brochure will include contact details, project details, objectives, methodology, start date, duration, EU funding information, social media account information, consortium details, and a QR code linking to the project's website.

To minimize environmental impact, all materials will be available as e-documents and printing will only occur as needed.

Table 8, Printed material KPIs

Printed material	
No. of hard copies	Roll -up Banners
>1,500	>6

4.2.2. E-newsletters and email campaigns

Nine e-newsletters will be released and distributed to the DigInTraCE mailing list. These newsletters will also be uploaded to a dedicated [Newsletters' section on the DigInTraCE website](#). Interested individuals can register for the newsletter through a designated section on the website. The first newsletter has already been issued.

Figure 10, DigInTraCE newsletter #1

Furthermore, dedicated email campaigns will be conducted to highlight important milestones or activities of the project. For both the newsletter and email campaigns, the Mailchimp platform will be used.

Table 9, E-newsletters and email campaigns' KPIs

E-Newsletters & email campaigns	
e-Newsletters contributed/released	Mailing List Contact Points
9	>2,000

4.2.3. Blogs

DigInTraCE will actively engage with open communities, DIHs, blogs, non - profit organisations and various channels to execute periodic broad promotion activities, starting from M18 of the project. As part of these activities, DigInTraCE partners will create a total of 8 blog posts, which will be available on the project's website.

Table 10, Blog posts KPIs

Blogs	
Unique Publications/Contributions to Blogs	Different Blogs to Post
>15	>8

4.2.4. Videos

The project will produce multimedia material to create self-explanatory and visually appealing presentations of the project. This material will be distributed through various channels, including YouTube, to effectively promote the project. Also, a series of video interviews will be conducted with scientific partners to gather valuable insights. These interviews will be conducted during plenary meetings and relevant events, in collaboration with the DigInTraCE capacity building activities.

Table 11, Videos' KPIs

Videos	
No. of short videos and interviews produced (in total)	Number of views
7	>10,000

4.3. Press activities

DigInTraCE will develop press releases in English, primarily handled by ICCS, to announce specific achievements of the project. These press releases will be distributed to various media communication channels such as local or national radio, television, and online press. All partners will be encouraged to translate the press release in their local language and use their press contacts to further disseminate the project's progress. A kick-off press release had been already created and is available on the DigInTraCE website, in the [news' section](#).

Furthermore, the partners will focus their efforts on publishing major DigInTraCE achievements through European Commission platforms such as Horizon Magazine, research*EU results magazine, Futuris Magazine and others. It is important to note that, as stated in the GA (Article 38), beneficiaries are required to inform the Agency before engaging in communication activities that are expected to have a significant media impact. This includes activities targeting the general public, such as interviews with the project coordinator on national TV or articles in national newspapers. The project coordinator is responsible for informing the Project Officer about such communication activities.

Figure 11, Kick-off Press Release

4.4. Events

DigInTraCE plans to organize its own dissemination events to showcase the project's results to a wider audience. These events will provide an opportunity for the consortium to engage with stakeholders, present their findings, and foster collaborations. It is acknowledged the importance for the project team to stay updated on relevant conferences, fairs, and meetings in the field and explore additional opportunities for dissemination and knowledge exchange.

To this regard, the following table presents a short list of identified international conferences and related events where DigInTraCE may present its outcomes. Please note that this list is not exhaustive, and it will be regularly updated to include further dissemination opportunities. The following versions of this deliverable will include the updated events' table. Relevant information regarding these events and any new additions will be communicated to the consortium via direct mailing on a regular basis.

Table 12, Events' list

Conference	Date	Place	Link
International Conference on Distributed Ledger Technology and Blockchain			https://waset.org/distributed-ledger-technology-and-blockchain-conference
ICWM 2024	21-23/02/2024	Japan	http://icwrm.org/
ICCSTP 2024	TBA	TBA	https://waset.org/clothing-sustainability-and-textile-processing-conference-in-april-2022-in-istanbul

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ICTES 2024	TBA	TBA	
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Table 13, Scientific conferences KPI

Scientific events
Presenting in Scientific Conferences
>20

4.5. Workshops and trainings

Special focus will be given to the co-design of training activities and lifelong learning programmes within DigInTraCE to ensure that the project contributes to establishing a digitally skilled population, as foreseen by task 7.2.

Table 14, Workshops & Trainings KPIs

Workshops & Trainings		
Technical Workshops	Online Training Tutorials	Webinars
>10 in 7 different countries	>8	>12

4.6. Networking and stakeholder engagement activities

To further amplify and maximise the impact and outreach of the project's results and to feed them into related international work streams, DigInTraCE will engage in joint dissemination activities through contracted collaborations. The project will explore synergies with other projects and initiatives (i.e., CE-RISE and Plooto; projects funded under the same Horizon Europe topic), and actively organize or participate in events promoting knowledge exchange as described in T7.4

Table 15, KPI for networking and stakeholder engagement activities

Networking and stakeholder engagement activities		
Symposiums/ Fairs	Banners in each event	Procures to be Distributed
>9	3	>300

4.7. Publications

4.7.1. Scientific Publications

DigInTraCE will prioritise the publication of peer-reviewed scientific papers in high-impact factor peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings. The project will aim to follow the Gold Open Access model whenever possible, ensuring that the peer-reviewed scientific articles resulting from the project are freely accessible to the public. In cases where the Gold Open Access model is not feasible, the project will consider the Green Open Access model as an alternative for making the research articles openly available.

Table 16, Initial list of journals

Journal	Link
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Digital Communications and Networks	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/digital-communications-and-networks
Recycling	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/recycling#:~:text=Recycling%20is%20an%20international%2C%20peer,b%20authors%20or%20their%20institutions.
Resources, Conservation and Recycling	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/resources-conservation-and-recycling
Journal of Material Processing Technology	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-materials-processing-technology
Polymer	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/polymer
Composites Science and Technology	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/composites-science-and-technology
Sustainability	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sustainability
Waste Management	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/waste-management
Wood Science and Technology	https://www.springer.com/journal/226

To support partners in their dissemination activities, a comprehensive list, including prestigious journals, will be provided to the Consortium, offering a range of publication opportunities. This list will be frequently updated to include additional dissemination opportunities as they arise. Relevant information regarding these opportunities will be shared with the Consortium on a regular basis through direct mailing to ensure everyone is informed. Moreover, partners are encouraged to use Open Research Europe, the new open access publishing platform, for publishing research stemming from Horizon Europe funding. To keep track of the project's publications, ICCS will maintain a list that includes both submitted and accepted publications. This will serve as a centralized record of the project's scientific contributions.

Table 17, Scientific Publications KPI

Scientific Publications	
Publishing in Peer-reviewed Journals	Presenting in Scientific Conferences
>15	>20

4.7.2. Technical Publications

In addition to the scientific publications, DigInTraCE will actively engage in publishing and contributing to technical blog posts, articles, position/white papers, catalogues, books and other reference. This includes collaborating with technology providers to share insights and advancements (bottom-up approach), as well as including references related to the application scenarios in the domains under consideration. For instance, DigInTraCE will contribute to [International Institute for Environment and Development](#) and [SPIRE database of the outputs from projects of SPIRE portfolio](#).

Table 18, Technical Publications KPIs

Technical Publications

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Publishing Technical Publications	Participation in Industrial Exhibitions with Booths
>25	>10

4.7.3. Standards and Policy Publications

DigInTraCE will support secondary material, AI and blockchain standardization. For this, there will be a strong linkage among T7.1 and T7.4. Collaboration with relevant standardization Technical Committees will be established to ensure effective integration into current and future standardization developments. DigInTraCE contribution will be included in the new or revised standards through one of the following channels: i) providing information to standardization Technical Committees, ii) engaging in mutual knowledge sharing, iii) submitting technical proposals, iv) promoting the development of new standard documents depending on the maturity of specific solutions as foreseen by T7.1. These contributions aim to support the development of robust standards that can be utilized by the industry. In addition, DigInTraCE will develop two policy briefs, each focused on the analysis sectors of pulp and paper, as well as chemicals and plastics.

Table 19, Standards and Policy Contribution KPIs

Standards and Policy Contribution	
Standards Contributions (new or revised)	Policy briefs
>5	>2

4.7.4. Source Code Publications

Encouraging a transparent and open-source culture, DigInTraCE will make accessible its software repositories through well-known distributed source code platforms, such as GitHub and Bitbucket.

Table 20, Source Code Publications KPIs

Source Code Publications	
Number of Publicly Available Deliverables	Source code published to
20	>2 different repositories

4.7.5. Q&A Platform

Conversations about the project repository would be concentrated in reference sites. The selected Q&A platform, developed as a part of project website will be the Stack Overflow, the largest, most trusted online community for developers to learn and share knowledge.

Table 21, Q&A Platform KPI

Q&A Platform
No. of Scientific Conversations to Participate/Contribute
>25

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4.8. Stakeholders' Hub

A stakeholders' hub will be established (M6) to involve different actors of the supply chains. All partners are required to suggest relevant actors so as to be part of the DigInTraCE Stakeholders' Hub. The hub's participants will be invited to the DigInTraCE events and will contribute to the project's developments through online meetings, questionnaires, surveys and other means.

5. Implementation of the Communication and Dissemination Plan

5.1. Partners' Role

MERIT is the WP7 leader and responsible for the Exploitation, Business models and IPR Management (T7.3). DS is the T7.1 leader, responsible for the standardization and certification schemes. The standardization activities held in this Task will provide inputs to the policy recommendations of T7.4 UBRUN is the T7.2 leader, responsible for co-designing training activities and lifelong learning programmes on digital skills, replication and cooperation. UBRUN will be in close collaboration with ICCS (T7.4 leader) contributing to dissemination and promoting best practice exchange among relevant EU projects and initiatives.

ICCS is responsible for managing and monitoring the communication and dissemination activities, as well as the policy recommendations. ICCS will be engaging with all project partners to ensure that the communication and dissemination activities of the project are effective and impactful. Additionally, all partners in the project play a crucial role in contributing to the communication and dissemination activities. They are encouraged to utilize their respective networks, channels, and expertise to effectively promote and disseminate the project's results. This includes participating in international events, publishing research papers and articles in relevant journals and conferences, and utilizing their online presence to raise awareness about the project. The collaboration between MERIT (WP7 leader), ICCS (T7.4 leader), and all project partners ensures that the communication and dissemination activities of DigInTraCE are comprehensive, well-coordinated, and impactful in reaching the target audiences and maximizing the project's visibility and impact.

Table 22, Partners' role in WP7

Partners' role	
Partner	WP7 PMs
ICCS	16
NTUA	1
UST	4
CIRCE	1.5
DS	17
IRIS	2
VTT	
MERIT	33
HTECH	13
CHIMAR	2.50
AGRST	1
MXS	4
TECNL	10

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TNLCERT	8
ASTI	9
CTB	14
SIOEN	3
DGS	1
SIGIT	2
UVQ	1
EUPC	5
UBRUN	7

It is important to mention that all partners have been asked to plan their dissemination activities (participation in events, social media presence) and fill in the appropriate forms. The template is available in Annex 3.

5.2. Roadmap and preliminary action plan

An initial communication roadmap has been configured, providing an overview of the way that the communications channels and tools will be used for reaching each of the specified key audiences. The roadmap provides an overview of the communication activities that will be carried out throughout the entire duration of the project, with a breakdown per year.

In this chapter, a preliminary action plan has been designed, presenting the specific actions that will be undertaken for each activity to ensure a comprehensive and successful communication of the project. It is important to note that the planned actions in the preliminary action plan may be subject to modifications as the project progresses and as the communication needs evolve. The flexibility to adapt the communication strategy and actions allows for adjustments to be made based on the project's requirements and changing circumstances. The updates on the status of the planned activities will be included in the respective deliverable's updates on M24 and M48.

Table 23, Communication and Dissemination roadmap & action plan

Roadmap and preliminary action plan				
Phase	Description	Communication Activities	Planned actions per activity	Milestones & deliverables

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<p>1st phase (M1-M12)</p>	<p>During the first year of the project, the communication activities aim to provide general information to the public, as well as relevant research, academic and industrial communities about the project's objectives, expected outcomes and results. In this initial phase, greater emphasis will be placed on communication activities. Dissemination efforts will focus on raising awareness and delivering information to relevant stakeholders about the project's concept, expected impact, and initial project's results.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brand identity design; • Communication kit development; • Project website creation; • Social media channels set up; • Media articles/interviews publication; • Press Releases' publication; • E-Newsletter publication; • Project presentations in conferences and other events; • Project presentations at relevant associations, organizations, fora and exhibitions; • Establish Networking activities with related projects; • Webinars organisation; • Blogs; • Stakeholders' Hub 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brand identity ready before the KoM; • 1st version of the banner ready for the KoM; • Social media launch before KoM; • Website launch by M3; • 1st version of the brochure ready by M4; • Social media followers by M12 >600; • 1 press release; • 2 media article/interviews; • 5 project presentations at conferences; • 2 participations in exhibition booths; • Connect with at least 2 relevant projects; • 2 e-newsletters published; • 1 webinar; • 2 blogs; • 2 Scientific conference presentations; • 3 technical publications; • Stakeholders' Hub establishment 	<p>D7.8 Communication and Dissemination plan and activities v1</p>
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2 nd phase (M13-M24)	<p>In this phase of the project some initial results will be available. Thus, the aim of dissemination within this period will be to publish the first developments and describe the future work to be performed.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website & social media updates; • Project presentations in conferences & events; • Project presentations in respective associations, organizations, fora and exhibitions; • Media articles/interviews publication; • E-Newsletter publication; • Establish Networking activities with related projects; • Organize online training tutorials; • Organize technical workshops; • Multimedia material production; • Webinars organisation; • Scientific conversations; • Blogs; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly updates on the website & social media; • Social media followers by M24 >1500; • 2 media articles/interviews (at least 1 in an EU media) • 3 peer-reviewed journal publications • 5 project presentations in respective associations, organizations etc. • organization of a joint webinar/special session with other projects • 2 e-newsletters published; • 2 online training tutorials organised; • 2 technical workshops organisation; • 2 participations in exhibition booths; • 1 roll-up banner; • 1 video/interview; • 2 webinars; • 5 scientific conversations; • 3 blogs; 	D7.9 Communication and Dissemination plan and activities v2
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 Scientific conference presentations; • 4 Technical publications; 	
3 rd phase (M25-M36)	<p>Within the third year of the project, more technical results will be available, thus there will be a major effort on disseminating the project results to all target groups.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website & social media updates; • Project presentations in conferences & events; • Project presentations in respective associations, organizations, fora and exhibitions; • Media articles/interviews publication; • E-Newsletter publication; • Establish Networking activities with related projects; • Organize technical workshops; • Multimedia material production; • Webinars organisation; • Scientific conversations; • Blogs; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 e-newsletters published; • 2 online training activities organised; • 4 technical workshops organisation; • 3 participations in exhibition booths; • 2 roll-up banners; • 3 videos/interviews; • 4 webinars; • 10 scientific conversations; • 4 blogs; • 6 Scientific conference presentations; • 5 peer-reviewed journal publications • 8 Technical publications; 	

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4 th phase (M37-M48)	In the final phase of the project, a major effort will be made in effectively disseminating the final project's results to the target audiences to maximize the exploitation and future use of the outcomes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organize technical workshops; • Multimedia material production; • Webinars organisation; • Scientific conversations; • Blogs; • Scientific presentations; • Final Conference; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8 Scientific conference presentations; • 3 e-newsletters published • 2 online training activities organised; • 4 technical workshops organisation; • 3 participations in exhibition booths; • 2 roll-up banners; • 3 videos/interviews; • 5 webinars; • 10 scientific conversations; • 6 blogs; • 7 peer-reviewed journal publications • 10 Technical publications; • Final Conference; 	D7.10 Communication and Dissemination plan and activities FINAL
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5.3. Dissemination Procedures

The participation of any partner in an event, as well as the publication or presentation of work conducted within the scope of DigInTraCE or any other dissemination activity related to the project, must receive prior approval from the DigInTraCE Consortium..

The detailed procedure outlining the steps to follow has been distributed to the consortium and is accessible on the Teams working space, as well as in Annex 2 of this deliverable.

5.4. EU acknowledgement

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According to the Article 17 of the GA, all communication activities related to the Action (media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the agent must acknowledge EU support and display the European emblem and funding statement.

Figure 12, EU funded emblem

In addition to the EU emblem, any communication or dissemination activity related to the action, must indicate the following disclaimer:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

6. Conclusions

DigInTraCE is expected to have a significant impact on the environmental sector by contributing to the development of circular and low-emission value chains through digitalization. To maximize this impact, the project aims to communicate its results to various target audiences, including the scientific community, policy makers, public authorities, environmental partnerships and associations, industries, end users and the general public.

The D7.8 'Communication and Dissemination plan and activities v1' provides an overview of the project's communication and dissemination strategy. It outlines the objectives, key audiences, and key messages to be conveyed. The plan also identifies the communication and dissemination channels that will be utilized.

DigInTraCE will employ a multi-disciplinary communication and dissemination approach, utilising a range of communication and dissemination tools, including but not limited to brochures, roll-up banners, videos, e-newsletters, press releases, social media presence, webinars, trainings, workshops and events. The effectiveness of these activities will be evaluated using carefully selected KPIs to ensure maximum impact of the project's results.

D7.8 Communication and Dissemination plan and activities v1 will be a dynamic document that will be adapted as needed. Updates will be made on M24 (D7.9 Communication and Dissemination plan and activities v2) and M48 (Communication and Dissemination plan and activities FINAL) to reflect the project's updates and progress against the planned actions per activity.

Annexes

Annex 1: DigInTraCE Templates

Figure 13, 1st slide of the ppt template

Figure 14, Last slide of the ppt template

Annex 2: Dissemination Procedures

Dissemination Procedure

Description and Purpose

The participation of any partner in an event, the publication or presentation of work done within the framework of DigInTraCE or the performance of any other dissemination activity related to the project has to be approved beforehand by the DigInTraCE Consortium.

The dissemination procedure is to be followed by all partners equally to:

- Produce high quality DigInTraCE publications and presentations;
- Avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- Efficiently monitor, record and promote the dissemination activities of the project;
- Secure the brand identity of the project and the EC rules to be followed.

The WP7 leader (MERIT) and the Task 7.4 leader (ICCS) are responsible for ensuring compliance with the procedures. **All partners are called to contribute efficiently on the dissemination of the project.**

Step by Step Procedure

Before any dissemination activity related to the DigInTraCE project, the initiator of the activity should:

STEP 1: Notify the Task 7.4 Leader (Dimitris Maragkos: dimitris.maragkos@iccs.gr) **at least 45 working days in advance** about the intention to participate on a dissemination activity, sharing a) the details of the activity (date of event, name of journal, title of activity, audience, etc.), b) their specific role in it (presenter, organiser, speaker in a session, etc.) and c) a short description (up to 150 words) of the activity and how it is related to DigInTraCE (See [Relevant information Table](#) below);

STEP 2: Register the activity in the applicable tab on the [Dissemination Register](#), specifying all the details regarding the activity, as indicated in each column of the file;

STEP 3: If applicable, store the relevant material (abstract, draft paper, poster, article, presentation, press release etc.) in the [WP7 Dissemination folder](#) on Teams, under the related sub-folder (Events, Publications or Other);

STEP 4: Task 7.4 leader has 2 days to react and send the request to the Consortium for approval, modification or rejection;

STEP 5: Any Consortium member may raise a modification or rejection request along with comments which should be sent to the Task 7.4 leader within 30 days; no response is considered as an approval;

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STEP 6: The Task 7.4 leader informs the initiator of the dissemination activity and the Project Coordinator about the decision.

In case of:

- a) Approval: The initiator may proceed with the submission or realization of the planned dissemination activity;
- b) Conflict/objection: Any Consortium member can object to the proposed dissemination activity, for example in cases of risk of disclosure of restricted or confidential information. The objection has to include a clear reasoning as well as a precise request for necessary modifications that would make the dissemination acceptable.

The issue is discussed among the Coordinator, the Task 7.4 Leader and the involved partners.

Dissemination Activities report

Within **ten working days** after the realisation of the dissemination activity, the partner should provide the Task 7.4 Leader with the filled in dissemination report (available on Teams) and the presented dissemination material (final paper, presentation, poster etc.). It will be also appreciated if the lead partner of every dissemination activity provides the WP7 Leader and Task 7.4 Leader with some photos of the participation at the event. The partners are requested to complete all the fields briefly and clearly, trying to avoid the use of abbreviations. The filled in report, as well as all the material received, will be archived by ICCS to the [Dissemination Activity Inventory](#) on Teams.

EU Acknowledgement

Since 2021, all recipients of EU funds have the legal obligation to explicitly acknowledge that their action has received EU funding. This requirement is to ensure visibility and transparency. For projects funded under Horizon Europe, this requirement is specified under Article 17 of the grant agreement. The obligation requires all beneficiaries, managing authorities and implementing partners of EU funding to acknowledge the support from the European Union on all communication materials. An important element with this regard is the European Union emblem and the funding statement

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HAEDA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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(available on Teams [here](#)), which must be displayed prominently¹ on all printed and digital products, websites, social media channels and other communication products:

**Funded by
the European Union**

Useful Links

Dissemination Folder	On Teams
Calendar of Events	Google Sheets
Dissemination Activities Register	Google Sheets
Dissemination Report	On Teams

Relevant information Table

TITLE OF ACTIVITY	
Description / Short Summary	
Relation to DigInTraCE	

¹The Use of the emblem in the context of EU Programmes 2021-2027:
https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2021-05/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf

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Annex 3: Individual Dissemination Plan template

Individual Dissemination Plan

NAME	
DATE	
CONTACT PERSON	

A) Participation in events

Participation in events (Conferences, Trade shows, Workshops, Online Events) Planned activities				
No.	Name of the event (Which event)	Date (When)	Place (Where)	What to present
1				
2				
3				
4				

B) Publications

Publications (journals, conference proceedings, magazines) Planned activities				
No.	Targeted journals / Conferences	Place (Where)	Topic planned to be elaborated (what)	Other partners to be involved as co-authors (name ONLY the organization)
1				
2				
3				
4				

C) Joint activities

Participation in joint activities with relevant projects				
No.	Name of sister project	Type of activity	Place	Date
1				
2				
3				
4				

D) Other communication activities

Participation in other communication activities					
No.	Name of the event	Type of activity	Place	Date	What to present
1					
2					
3					
4					

Annex 4: Initial logo designs for voting (logo poll)

Logo 01

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DIGINTRACE_LOGO_01

Logo 02

DIGINTRACE_LOGO_01

Logo 03

DIGINTRACE_LOGO_01